

POLICY BRIEF 2

**Advancing Gender Equality in Academia for Sustainability,
Competitiveness and Economic Growth in Central and Eastern
Europe (CEE)**

Project data

Project Title:	Assessment and implementation of Agriculture and Life Science Universities' first Gender Equality Plans in widening countries
Project Grant Agreement (GA) No:	101094158
Project Acronym:	AGRIGEP
Duration:	36 months
Type of action:	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Start date of Project:	01-01-2023

Deliverable Administration and Summary

Status:	Final-revised	Due:	M36	Date:	31/12/ 2025
Author (s)	All partners				
Reviewers	Marta Peña (UPC)				
WP	5	Deliverable Nr.	D5.3	Relative Nr.	D17
Comments	The Deliverable 1.5, "Policy Brief 1: Implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Higher Education and Research in Widening Countries: The case of Agriculture & Life Sciences," is the relevant antecedent of the current document.				

Document change history

Version	Date	Author	Description
0.1	21/11/2025	Kobolak, J.; Kocsis-Kiss, M.; Mazancova, J.; Bojnec, S.; Paksi, V.	First draft
0.2	22/11/2025	Marta Peña	Review of and input to the first draft
0.3	24/12/2025	Maxime Forest	Review of and input to the first draft
0.4	05/12/2025	Mazancova, J.	revised second version
0.5	08/12/2025	Kobolak, J.	revised third version
0.6	17/12/2025	Mazancova, J.	revised third version
1.0	18/12/2025	Kobolak, J.	Version for submission

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How to cite this policy brief: AGRIGEP consortium (2025): Advancing Gender Equality in Academia for Sustainability, Competitiveness and Economic Growth in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE). Policy Brief 2 of the AGRIGEP project (Horizon Europe 101094158)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20796238

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01 programme under grant agreement no. 101094158

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Advancing Gender Equality in Academia for Sustainability, Competitiveness and Economic Growth in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE)

1. Objectives of the document

This policy brief distils lessons and enablers for promoting gender equality through first-time GEPs of the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) participating in the AGRIGEP project, and how they tackled implementation challenges with concrete measures and strategies. The AGRIGEP implementing partners are located in Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, which are designated as “widening countries”¹ in the context of the European Union’s research policies. The participating HEIs’ challenges may be similar to those faced by other universities in widening countries that are developing and implementing their first Gender Equality Plan (GEP); therefore, their strategies and measures could serve as relevant examples for others, especially in the agriculture and life sciences (ALS) sectors of higher education and research. Our aim here was to provide a comprehensive assessment of the advancement of these organisations, highlighting solutions and strategies that were efficient in their local context, embedding GE norms into institutional strategic frameworks and documents, and advancing GE at the organisational level through broader (local or regional policy) networks.

This document is inseparable from and builds upon “*Policy Brief 1: Implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Higher Education and Research in Widening Countries: The case of Agriculture & Life Sciences*”² which reviewed the main difficulties and hindrances encountered by these institutions, providing comprehensive information on their background, both on organisational (intrinsically gendered academic institutions), sectoral (STEM field and the subsectors of agriculture and related life sciences), societal and policy (widening countries in CEE) levels. These barriers were thoroughly analysed and presented in a comprehensive empirical research article as well³. While Policy Brief 1 mapped the structural barriers and the initial conditions, Policy Brief 2 focuses on the evolution of implementation capacities, institutional learning, and the development of sector-specific strategies that emerged during the AGRIGEP project. It provides actionable insights for institutions that have already passed the initial compliance stage.

Most HEIs and Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) in widening countries developed their first formal GEPs in line with the Horizon Europe mandatory GEP rule from 2022, independently of the prior existence of gender equality policies and respective in-house expertise. Therefore, several organisations are just completing their first cycle and developing – or will soon develop – their next generation of GEPs. This document also emphasises the unique characteristics of the agriculture and life sciences sector, where fieldwork, laboratory environments, engagement with rural communities and external work placements, along with the difficulties of the agri-business sector, create specific gender-related challenges and require a dedicated strategic approach. We emphasise the use of context- and sector-

¹ Reducing disparities in EU R&I by sharing knowledge and expertise helps eligible countries strengthen their global competitiveness and enables the EU to tap the full R&I potential of all Member States. Further action, such as promoting open, diverse consortia, is needed to prevent closed collaborations, include newcomers, and maximise the benefits of Europe’s talent pool across the EU. Under the Horizon Europe Regulation, “Widening countries” include 15 EU Member States (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia), 14 associated countries (as of 1 June 2022: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, North Macedonia, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine), and 9 EU outermost regions (as defined in Art. 349 TFEU: French Guiana, Guadeloupe, Martinique, Mayotte, Réunion, Saint-Martin, the Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands). <https://www.horizontevropa.cz/en/he-programme-structure/widening-participation-strengthening-era/widening-participation-spreading-excellence/information?storiesType=0>

² AGRIGEP Project (2023): Implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Higher Education and Research in widening countries: The case of agriculture & life sciences. Policy Brief 1 of the AGRIGEP project (Horizon Europe 101094158) [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14795538](https://zenodo.org/record/14795538)

³ Paksi et al. (2025) Gender Equality Barriers in Agriculture and Life Sciences in Central European Universities. Social Inclusion, 13, Article 10086. [DOI: 10.17645/si.10086](https://doi.org/10.17645/si.10086)

specific solutions to complement more generic tools and achieve progress in GE. We highlight the importance of addressing local context and connecting the GE strategy and implementation with existing methods and broader initiatives to overcome cultural and institutional barriers and resistances. Furthermore, we present the importance of developing local networks by engaging stakeholders and strengthening existing alliances. The tailored responses presented in this deliverable result from a learning process that began with a comprehensive assessment, intensive capacity building, and strategy development, supported by the mentor organisations⁴ of the AGRIGEP project.

The project served as a vital driving force for enhancing GE in the institutions of participating widening partners, providing critical knowledge, learning opportunities, and resources that facilitated progress. Advancing gender equality in the agriculture and life science (ALS) higher education and research sector has substantial policy relevance for the European Research Area (ERA), as it strengthens institutional competitiveness, supports innovation in agri-food systems, contributes to sustainability transitions, and enhances the economic resilience of CEE countries.

There is currently limited evidence on how widening-country HEIs progress after their first GEP cycle, especially in agriculture and life science ALS-focused institutions. Therefore, this document also aims to provide guidance to HEIs and RPOs in designing the next generation of their GEPs by highlighting effective enablers, context-responsive approaches, and mechanisms that could ensure sustainable gender equality reforms in the long term.

Whereas Policy Brief 1 provided an initial diagnosis of structural barriers, Policy Brief 2 moves beyond challenge identification and targets institutions that have already passed the compliance stage, offering practice-oriented guidance for second-generation GEP development in the context of widening countries. This Policy Brief, therefore, serves as both a reflection on institutional learning and a roadmap for HEIs and RPOs preparing their second-generation GEPs in the ALS sector.

2. AGRIGEP Project as a Driving Force for GEP 2.0 in the CEE Context

The AGRIGEP project, with the joint efforts of six consortium partners, aimed to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the status of widening country HEI partners in their GEP implementation, improve capabilities through intensive capacity building, and develop an agriculture and life-science (ALS)-targeted GEP 2.0 with sector-specific measures and strategies.

Implementation trajectories differ significantly across CEE countries due to variations in institutional autonomy, political engagement with equality agendas, and demographic or labour-market pressures that shape the academic environment. Recognising these differences is essential to avoid one-size-fits-all gender equality strategies. Furthermore, the agriculture and life sciences (ALS) sector presents unique gendered risks related to fieldwork safety, laboratory environments, external internships, and social norms in rural areas — that may differ from those in urban areas — and require targeted, strategic responses beyond generic STEM-oriented policies.

The AGRIGEP project ran from 2023 to 2025, a 36-month ERA project focused on capacity-building and skills development within participating HEIs to facilitate institutional transformation and advance GE. This project is only the first, but very important, step on the road to enhancing GE at HEIs, resulting in significant progress in the GE agenda across all institutions in a targeted manner.

The GEP-implementing HEIs of the AGRIGEP project are located in the Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovenia (widening countries), while the mentor organisations come from Spain and Belgium. The third mentor partner is an NGO operating in Hungary⁴. Based on Eurostat's aggregated data (2024)⁵, in the Gender Equality Index (GEI) — which measures 31 indicators in six key areas (work, money, knowledge, time, power, health) — Czechia (22nd place) and Hungary (26th place) lag behind Slovenia (ranking 13th)

⁴ Yellow Window, Belgium; Polytechnic University of Catalonia, Spain (UPC), Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE)

⁵ EIGE Gender Equality Index. 2024 <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2024/compare-countries>

among the 27 EU member states (Figure 1). Yet, the widening countries, particularly those in the CEE region, have shown only moderate progress towards GE since joining the EU^{6, 7}. Whereas significant progress has been made in widening countries concerning policy frameworks preventing gender-based discrimination, access to decision-making, and access to higher education and employment, some patterns of segregation and hierarchies remain. Moreover, changes in the unequal distribution of care work or the gender pay gap still tend to be slower than in other EU member states⁶. These differences highlight the uneven readiness of CEE institutions to improve their GE status, pointing to the need for national and regional policy support. Countries with weaker GE infrastructure may require additional incentives to build/strengthen their GE capacities, as well as regulatory guidance and external monitoring, to achieve comparable levels of progress in the higher education and research sector.

Figure 1. Gender Equality Index Map

The status of gender (in)equality in each country is rooted in specific, socially and historically constructed arrangements described in the literature⁸ as “gender regimes”, which designate the combination of the sexual division of labour, the distribution of power, and patterns of social interactions deriving from cultural representations. It is also path-dependent on recent political and economic transformation processes, such as the transition from state socialism and authoritarianism to liberal market democracy⁹, or the harmonisation of policies and politics with the EU⁵, and influenced by broader societal change, such as those driven by the digital revolution¹⁰. Understanding these structural and historical dynamics is essential for designing effective GE interventions in ALS-focused HEIs, where

⁶ Spehar, A (2021). Europeanization and the challenge of gender equality. in Fábíán K., Johnson K.E., and Lazda M. (eds). The Routledge Handbook of Gender in Central-Eastern Europe and Eurasia. Routledge. p379.

<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781138347762-63/europeanization-challenge-gender-equality-andrea-spehar>

⁷ Forest, M. (2021) Europeanization in Abels G., MacRae, H., Kriszan, A. and van der Vleuten, A. (eds.). The Routledge Handbook of Gender and EU Politics, Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781351049955-4/europeanization-maxime-forest>

⁸ Walby, S. (2020). Varieties of Gender Regimes, *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 27(3), 414–431, <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxaa018>

⁹ Gradska, Y., Asztalos Morell, I. (eds.) (2020). *Gendering Postsocialism. Old Legacies and New Hierarchies*. Routledge.

¹⁰ Deloitte. (2015). From brawn to brains. The impact of technology on jobs in the UK. <https://www2.deloitte.com/uk/en/pages/growth/articles/from-brawn-to-brains%2D%2Dthe-impact-of-technology-on-jobs-in-the-u.html>

cultural norms, rural traditions¹¹, and sector-specific hierarchies often amplify gender disparities. Tailored policy responses must therefore account for both national gender regimes and the particular characteristics of ALS education and research.

As acknowledged in various policy reports on progress in achieving the European Research Area's (ERA) objectives on GE¹², both difficulties and successes are unevenly distributed across the EU. The gender gap in higher education and research largely coincides with the knowledge and innovation gap in less research-intensive widening countries. Advancing gender equality in higher education and research, in line with UN SDG5¹³, is vital for social progress, economic growth, sustainability, and equity. Gender equality strengthens diversity, driving innovation and solutions to complex challenges¹⁴. Universities and research organisations, entrusted with the public good, must uphold high standards in governance, teaching, and science while fostering inclusive communities¹⁵. Yet persistent GE barriers are compounded by the rise of neoliberal governance in higher education, which demands targeted policy responses. In widening countries, these pressures are further intensified by resource constraints, limited visibility, the existence of gender equality expertise, and the slower pace of governance reforms. As revealed by AGRIGEP, institutional progress is achievable, but only when HEIs receive sustained political, financial, and organisational support aligned with ERA-level objectives.

When we focus on subsectors, such as the agriculture and life sciences sector, gender challenges differ from those encountered in other fields, including STEM, both in academia and in broader agri-food production¹⁶. Therefore, GEP implementation requires a strategy that addresses both the “widening country”-related gaps in CEE and the national societal and policy contexts regarding gender equality, as well as the sectoral challenges that require tailored responses. Moreover, agri-food systems are undergoing rapid transformation due to climate change, digitalisation, and labour-market shifts. Policies promoting gender-responsive innovation, equitable participation in field and laboratory environments, and safe working conditions in external placements are therefore essential to strengthening both educational quality and sector competitiveness.

Competitiveness is a key factor in Europe in all sectors, including research, development and innovation. In this sector, HEIs and RPOs are vital players, and the EU's Gender Equality Strategy is an inclusive scientific excellence framework consistently pursued and strengthened¹⁷. Competitiveness requires excellence, but excellence in research cannot be achieved if the institutions conducting the research are not themselves excellent. Organisations where not all can thrive, where there are inequalities, where people give up their careers and flee the sector, cannot perform to the best of their abilities. Competitiveness requires that basic conditions are fulfilled, and inclusiveness, respect, gender equality and safe working environments are among these. When gender equality is part of strategies, the benefits include diverse perspectives, better decision-making, increased performance and productivity,

¹¹ Czech and Hungarian agriculture / rural communities have been heavily affected by collectivisation in the late 1950s, and there is virtually nothing (or very little) left from rural traditions, even after the reestablishment of private and family farming in 1990 (the latter accounting for a very small share of agricultural production, at least in CR).

Brychta, J., Pacina, J., Novák, P. et al. Using defunct municipal field roads to implement low-cost anti-erosion measures in the ownership-fragmented landscape of the Czech Republic. *Sci Rep* 15, 22527 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-04407-4>

¹² GENDERACTION (2020). https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.2_MonitoringERApriority4implementation.pdf

¹³ UN SDG Goals. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/node/36060>

¹⁴ Rosa et al. (2020). Gender equality in higher education and research. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 31(1), 1-7. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/09589236.2022.2007446>

¹⁵ See: RESET Joint Statement for Equality, Diversity, and Excellence in Research: https://wereset.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Joint-statement-RESET_website.pdf

¹⁶ Pyburn, R. and van Eerdewijk, A. (2021). Advancing gender equality through agricultural and environmental research: Past, present, and future. [Washington, DC: International Food Policy Research Institute \(IFPRI\). https://doi.org/10.2499/9780896293915](https://doi.org/10.2499/9780896293915)

¹⁷ A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 COM(2020) 152; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0152>

market responsiveness, improved reputation, compliance with legal and ethical standards, and advancement in innovation, problem-solving, employee commitment, and morale, which increase the competitiveness of the ERA. This contextual background demonstrates that gender equality is not merely a social objective but a structural prerequisite for excellence in the ALS domain.

3. The Roadmap towards Advanced Gender Equality Organisational Culture

In the AGRIGEP project, GEP-implementing HEIs used a strategic framing approach to review their GEPs. It served to (1) assess how effectively the first GEP addressed institutional GE issues and (2) integrate GE promotion into overall institutional strategy while developing GEP 2.0. For widening-country HEIs, it acted as a stabilising mechanism, helping build coherent processes and align GE efforts with organisational priorities.

The strategic framing followed six steps (Figure 2). Along the road, the AGRIGEP project contributed to creating an enabling environment for the elaboration of GEP 2.0 at widening HEIs through assessment and monitoring, internal capacity building, continuous mentoring, and peer learning.

Figure 2. AGRIGEP Roadmap towards GEP 2.0

A **systematic assessment and monitoring** identified gaps across key areas, providing each HEI with a clear picture of where to improve. This roadmap was especially important for widening-country institutions with limited data, gender expertise and equality structures, ensuring GE work could progress even with scarce resources and little prior experience. Tailored capacity building then addressed identified needs, providing systematic training in skills, knowledge and competencies while helping institutions internalise gender-equality principles, reduce resistance and generate internal demand for change. **Continuous mentoring** and repeated self-assessments supported an integrated monitoring system, building on previous GE projects and adapting them to local contexts. This robust monitoring architecture strengthens accountability, demonstrates progress to funders and policymakers, and improves transparency, which is often incomplete in CEE HEIs. By institutionalising monitoring practices, HEIs can sustain GE efforts beyond the project lifecycle. Together, these elements laid the foundations for next-generation GEPs (GEP 2.0) that better reflect local contexts, integrate sustainability and reinforce ongoing institutional reforms. Following a structured model ensured that GEP 2.0 development was evidence-based, context-responsive and aligned with ERA expectations for long-term change. It also strengthened internal accountability in widening-country institutions and enabled step-by-step, systematic progress that can serve as a good practice for others.

Below, we highlight a few critical points that underpinned our efforts and may serve as a valuable reference for other institutions embarking on similar GE processes.

- **Building on existing knowledge and experiences**, a systematic literature review and analysis of previous GE projects informed the planning phase and clarified priority areas. This step is especially important for “newcomers” with limited gender data and GE experience. Systematic data collection and analysis help identify strategic priorities, provide a solid basis for planning and subsequent monitoring, and enable HEIs to justify their strategies to national authorities, accreditation bodies, and EU-level funders with evidence rather than assumptions.
- **Assessing institutional capabilities and capacities:** Capacity building was identified as a crucial area for AGRIGEP project partners, though focus differed. The institutional needs-based capacity assessment is crucial for developing effective strategies. Without it, progress stalls, and systemic gaps, such as shortages of trained GE staff, limited gender expertise, and insufficient internal support structures, persist, highlighting the need for national and institutional policies that invest in long-term personnel development.
- **Stakeholder Engagement: Internal discussions and awareness-raising are key to strategy-building;** however, forums for discussing equal opportunities are often lacking, thus information fails to reach decision-makers. Beginners often underestimate the importance of awareness-raising events and materials, even though they are crucial for effective communication and engagement. Creating channels for information flow, surveys, and feedback, and embedding these dialogue mechanisms into routine practice, ensures that stakeholders' perceptions of GE and inequality inform both strategy development and implementation.

The evolution of stakeholders' engagement in the widening RPOs in the AGRIGEP project is shown in Figure 3. The figure illustrates how AGRIGEP supports research-performing organisations (RPOs) in transitioning from GEP 1.0, which is driven by eligibility requirements, toward a more participatory GEP 2.0 approach. In WP2 (work package), partners carry out stakeholder mapping by applying the tool developed in the SUPERA project¹⁸ at project months 12 and 24, co-create insights through joint sessions, and regularly update stakeholder maps to reflect stakeholders' roles, interests, and influence. The mapping outputs (including a SWOT) feed into a structured engagement strategy—active outreach, more transparent external communication of GE(P) results, and ongoing monitoring and evaluation. Together, these steps inform GEP 2.0 drafting and

¹⁸ <https://www.superaproject.eu/>

broaden staff, HR, equality bodies, student services, and unions' involvement, enabling a shift from compliance-driven actions to co-creative processes sustained through months 12–36.

- **Increasing and strengthening managers' commitment.** The support of the top management is decisive; without it, even a well-designed strategy may fail. Managers need to be informed, involved, and shown how GE advances broader institutional development goals, such as research excellence, internationalisation, and sustainability. Clear communication, positive reinforcement, and aligning GE measures with core institutional priorities and performance systems strengthen ownership. From a policy perspective, leadership commitment and the integration of GE into governance, assessment, and strategic planning are among the strongest predictors of successful and stable GEP institutionalisation.

Together, these steps demonstrate that institutional transformation in widening countries requires not only technical tools (indicators, monitoring systems), but also the commitment of managers, the professionalisation of GE roles, and integration with broader institutional development agendas.

Figure 3. Evolution of Stakeholder Engagement at RPOs in the AGRIGEP Project

4. AGRIGEP Widening Partners Struggles and Mitigation Strategies

AGRIGEP widening partners faced a shared set of structural challenges that shaped how their GEPs 1.0 were designed and implemented. Early plans were often compliance-driven, under-resourced and weakly linked to institutional strategies. Leadership commitment was uneven and sometimes constrained by “family mainstreaming” narratives. ALS universities typically had limited gender expertise, siloed social science knowledge, and a false sense of “numbers are fine” because student gender ratios appeared balanced. At the same time, agriculture’s perceived low status and gendered stereotypes along the education pipeline made it harder to attract and retain diverse talent. In response, AGRIGEP widening partners used the project as a learning space to reframe GEPs as strategic tools, leverage EU frameworks, build cross-disciplinary alliances for academic freedom, invest in tailored capacity-building and teaching examples, use data to uncover hidden inequalities, and support outreach and challenge-based education that links ALS studies with climate, animal welfare, social justice and gender equality. Table 1 summarises these struggles and the corresponding mitigation strategies developed and implemented within the AGRIGEP.

Table 1. AGRIGEP Widening Partners: Challenges and Used Mitigation Strategies

Struggle	Description	AGRIGEP Strategies
Compliance-driven GEPs with weak ownership	Many first-generation GEPs were drafted primarily to satisfy EU or national requirements for project eligibility; they were thin documents with limited budgets, weak governance and little connection to institutional strategies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using AGRIGEP as a learning space where widening HEIs (incl. their leaders) could see how more mature institutions treat GEPs as strategic instruments, not bureaucracy. Framing GEP 2.0 as part of broader reforms (HR excellence, digitalisation, sustainability) and highlighting links between strong equality policies and improved ranking or competitiveness.
Ambivalent leadership and political backlash	In several widening contexts, political discourse has shifted towards “family mainstreaming” or anti-gender narratives, and leaders face mixed incentives. Some recognise the importance of gender equality; others fear controversy or see it as externally imposed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leveraging EU-level frameworks (Horizon Europe eligibility, upcoming ERA Act) as external legitimacy. Building alliances across disciplines to defend a single notion of academic freedom that includes work on equality, diversity and inclusion, not treating it as optional or separate from “real science”.
Limited gender expertise and siloed knowledge	ALS universities often have small sociology or gender teams, while most agricultural scientists lack basic training in social and gender analysis. Social data from projects are frequently “handed off” to social scientists and not reintegrated into mainstream ALS research or teaching.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint capacity-building with mentors and sister projects, including summer schools and webinars, to demystify concepts like living labs, co-creation and intersectionality for ALS staff. Developing discipline-relevant teaching examples and case portfolios for life sciences, so gender is seen as integral to excellence and innovation rather than as an external add-on.
Gender fatigue, scepticism and “numbers are fine” narratives	Because many ALS programmes have roughly balanced numbers of male and female students, colleagues often argue that “we don’t have a problem like STEM does”. This numerical focus obscures inequalities in leadership, evaluation, informal culture and sectoral labour markets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using data and qualitative evidence (focus groups, interviews) to surface hidden issues such as stereotypes, harassment, unequal care burdens and biased evaluation. Reframing gender equality not as a favour to women but as a prerequisite for high-quality teaching, research and green transitions in agriculture and food systems.
Pipeline challenges and attractiveness of agriculture	Beyond university walls, agriculture is often perceived as low-status or “old-fashioned,” and many STEM outreach activities for girls focus on engineering or IT, rather than ALS. Research suggests that until around age 10–11, girls and boys show similar interest in technical subjects; after this age, gendered stereotypes become stronger.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting national associations and outreach initiatives that target girls in upper-primary and secondary schools, dismantling stereotypes about ALS careers. Using challenge-based education and sustainability projects within HEIs to make ALS more appealing and show its relevance to climate, animal welfare and social justice – explicitly asking students to integrate gender into their projects.

5. Lessons Learned from AGRIGEP – Suggestions for HEIs and RPOs in CEE

Across AGRIGEP, partners implemented GEP-related measures from very different starting points (e.g. GE maturity, strategic framing, and existing services), and systematically exchanged what worked, what did not, and why. The **ten key lessons** below distil these shared experiences into recurring **problems faced** and **align with AGRIGEP best practices**. We place a specific focus on the structural constraints typical of ALS-focused HEIs in CEE (limited resources, ALS-specific barriers, and the need for deeper institutional reform) to support evidence-informed decision-making for **GEP 2.0** preparation and implementation. The lessons are ordered from broader, system-level issues to more specific, operational ones.

Lesson 1: Moving beyond compliance to real ownership

Many first-generation GEPs in CEE widening contexts were primarily drafted to meet eligibility or policy requirements and often remained “documents on paper” with limited budgets, weak governance, and weak links to institutional strategy. AGRIGEP partners learned that GEPs only become effective when grounded in **local realities and aligned with regional and institutional policies**, and used the practices outlined below.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- Use the project as a **learning space**, peer learning among widening HEIs and mentoring from more mature institutions helps reposition GEPs as strategic instruments, not bureaucracy.

- **Frame GEP 2.0 within broader reforms** (HR excellence, digitalisation, sustainability, wellbeing): explicitly show how strong equality policies support competitiveness (e.g., rankings), recruitment quality and access to funding. Utilise such narratives in both internal and external communication.
- **Adopt realistic, incremental implementation in rigid systems:** in rigid, hierarchical systems, rapid change can provoke resistance, whereas systematic, incremental development is more likely to stick. Progress should be judged less by speed and more by how well measures are consolidated into institutional strategies and routines, alongside growing awareness and capacity.
- **Institutionalise through governance and accountability:** clear mandates, procedures, accountability lines, and routine self-assessment prevent GEP measures from remaining “project add-ons.”
- **Stabilise resources beyond project cycles:** multi-year planning, ring-fenced GE lines, co-funding schemes, and minimum reporting requirements reduce ad hoc implementation and support sustainability. Resources must include staff time, dedicated roles, training and analytical capacity, not only funding.
- **Combine top-down and bottom-up action:** secure leadership backing while enabling staff/student initiatives to build ownership and legitimacy, because top-down-only approaches often remain formalistic and weakly implemented, while bottom-up-only efforts rarely gain the authority, resources, and policy anchoring needed for lasting structural change.
- Strengthen and formally recognise **change agents:** dedicated GEP teams were decisive drivers of reform; their role should be visible, valued and protected in organisational rules.

Lesson 2: Making leadership engagement possible under ambivalence or backlash

Building legitimacy, alliances and management ownership: In some contexts, “anti-gender” or “family mainstreaming” narratives and risk-avoidant leadership reduce willingness to engage. Leaders may see the GE agenda as disruptive, costly, or externally imposed.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Leverage EU-level frameworks as external legitimacy:** link the GEP to Horizon Europe eligibility, ERA expectations, accreditation/quality frameworks and institutional strategy to reduce perceptions of “optional” or “imposed” agendas.
- **Move management from resistance to value creation:** address cultural norms, inertia and perceived threats to power/resources through training (incl. mandatory modules for middle management), clear Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and transparent progress reporting.
- **Build alliances across disciplines and roles:** protect a shared understanding of academic freedom that includes equality, diversity and inclusion, rather than treating GE as separate from “real science.”
- **Make leadership engagement the decisive lever:** embed GE criteria into leadership selection, promotion systems and institutional evaluation frameworks so progress does not depend on individual champions.
- **Support women’s leadership pathways:** role models, mentoring and targeted programmes increase readiness to apply for senior roles, paired with transparent promotion systems and explicit leadership commitment.
- **Communicate proactively:** a dedicated internal and external communication strategy helps prevent misunderstandings, improves stakeholder engagement, and strengthens support from

fundlers, policymakers and community partners. Continuous, well-planned information and awareness-raising are essential for effective GEP design and implementation. This work requires specialised communication expertise, dedicated staff time and an adequate budget. In unfavourable environments, strong skills in communicating GE topics are particularly important for reaching stakeholders and building alliances across the university and beyond.

Lesson 3: Closing the expertise gap and breaking silos in ALS

Capacity-building that makes GE usable in ALS disciplines: ALS institutions often have limited internal gender expertise, while social science insights remain siloed and are not consistently integrated into mainstream research, HR, or teaching. At the same time, ALS work creates sector-specific contexts (fieldwork, laboratories, external placements, mobility) where generic GEP measures may miss concrete equality and safety needs.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Create a dedicated ALS thematic area in the GEP (sector-specific pillar):** rather than dispersing ALS issues across generic GE areas, a stand-alone ALS element helps address specific challenges and enables clearer monitoring of effects. Key ALS areas include:
 - **Fieldwork:** measures supporting GE in fieldwork, including equal opportunities and safety.
 - **Laboratory work:** measures supporting GE in labs, including equal opportunities and safety.
 - **External workplaces** (farms, agribusiness, industry partners): safe and equitable environments, reflected in cooperation agreements/MoUs/training contracts; clear statements of GE commitments to partners involved in teaching and R&I.
 - **Mobility and short-term stays/secondments** (incl. outside the EU): extend GE considerations and safeguards to these settings.
 - **Work-life balance:** strengthened support for women and students with young children participating in fieldwork, study trips or secondments.
 - **Inclusion and cultural diversity:** measures promoting mutual understanding, involving student organisations and reaching both international and national students.
- **Joint capacity-building with mentors and sister projects:** summer schools, webinars and peer exchange help demystify key concepts (e.g., co-creation, living labs, intersectionality) and build a shared language across ALS staff.
- **Make GE discipline-relevant:** develop ALS-specific teaching and research examples/case portfolios so gender is understood as part of excellence and innovation, not a separate add-on.
- **Provide hands-on support for research and teaching:** mentoring and advisory services (including examples from successful projects) increase researchers' and teachers' confidence to integrate the gender dimension into research content and everyday teaching practice; regular training plus feedback mechanisms are essential for slower-changing issues such as bias awareness.
- **Build reliable support structures:** where internal expertise is minimal, combine a committed internal core team with external experts and national/international networks, especially for HR and management units that often remain administrative rather than strategic.
- **Institutionalise roles and responsibilities:** formalise GE-related posts (e.g., GEP officer/equality referent), workloads, procedures and accountability lines in organisational rules and strategic documents to anchor capacity over time.

- **Policy-facing recommendation:** support this sectoral approach through tailored guidelines, targeted funding, and the integration of gender-sensitive requirements into agricultural education and innovation frameworks.

Lesson 4: Responding to “numbers are fine” and gender fatigue with evidence and relevance

Shift the debate from headcounts to lived realities and quality. Gender fatigue, scepticism, and “numbers are fine” narratives: Balanced student numbers can mask more profound inequalities in leadership, evaluation, informal culture, harassment risks, and unequal care burdens, fuelling so scepticism around the importance and impact of GE(P).

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Use robust quantitative and qualitative evidence:** combine monitoring systems with regular focus groups/interviews to surface hidden barriers (stereotypes, harassment, biased evaluation, care penalties) across internal stakeholders.
- **Integrate self-assessment as a continuous mechanism:** regular review of progress and achievements using appropriate tools is essential to tailor institution-specific strategies, track change over time, and allow for effective adaptive management.
- **Reframe GE as a quality prerequisite:** position gender equality as enabling high-quality teaching, research performance and green transitions in agriculture and food systems, not as a symbolic initiative.
- **Strengthen stakeholder engagement:** map interests, align goals with stakeholder priorities and shift from ad hoc activities to a structured engagement strategy (events, workshops, joint initiatives). Utilise co-creative methodologies for turning stakeholders from passive actors into co-owners of solutions, increasing relevance, trust, and long-term uptake of GEP measures.
- **Improve visibility and targeting of communication:** poor targeting and missing channels fuel scepticism; consistent, well-planned communication reduces misunderstandings and increases participation.

Lesson 5: Strengthening the pipeline and improving the attractiveness of agriculture

Make ALS visible, future-oriented, and safe/equitable in practice: Agriculture can be perceived as low-status or “old-fashioned,” and outreach often prioritises engineering/IT. Gendered stereotypes are established early, reducing future enrolment and retention.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Support national associations and outreach to girls (upper-primary/secondary):** dismantle stereotypes early and showcase ALS as modern, science-driven and socially relevant.
- **Use challenge-based education and sustainability projects:** make ALS more appealing through real-world problems (climate, animal welfare, social justice, the UN Sustainable Development Goals) and explicitly ask students to integrate gender into project design.
- **Treat ALS-specific issues as a dedicated GEP thematic area** (see Lesson 3 for details): sector-specific measures are easier to design, implement and monitor when grouped coherently.
- **Prioritise safety and equal opportunities in fieldwork, labs and external workplaces:** integrate GE commitments into cooperation agreements/MoUs with farms, agribusinesses and industry partners, including placement guidelines and student safety provisions.
- **Extend safeguards to mobility and short-term stays abroad (incl. outside the EU).**

- **Strengthen support for caregivers:** targeted measures for staff/students with young children participating in fieldwork, secondments and study trips.
- **Promote inclusion and mutual understanding:** involve student organisations to support cultural diversity and gender equality across both international and national student populations.
- Make **ALS careers visible** through role models, modern lab/field innovation stories, and pathways into high-impact jobs.

Lesson 6: Resources are the decisive factor and must be understood broadly

GE work is frequently under-resourced, and recent shocks (COVID-19 and rising energy prices) have further squeezed university budgets and pushed GE lower on institutional priority lists. When GEP implementation depends mainly on external project funding, activities become ad hoc, stop-start, and vulnerable once grants end. In addition, resourcing is often understood too narrowly as “money,” while the real bottlenecks also include staff time, dedicated roles, training capacity, and data/analytical support.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- Link GE to **high-priority institutional strategic goals** (rankings, HR development - HR Excellence in Research¹⁹, wellbeing, student/staff satisfaction) to protect resources during budget pressure.
- Introduce **multi-year planning**, ring-fenced GE lines, and co-funding schemes where feasible. A dedicated GE budget is a necessary first step, even before full gender budgeting is feasible.
- Define resources broadly: **staff time, dedicated posts, training, analytical capacity**, not only activities and events.
- Strengthen accountability through **minimum GE budget requirements** and basic financial reporting on GE measures to support institutionalisation and align with ERA expectations for transparent and equitable implementation.

Lesson 7: Organisational culture change is continuous and requires governance

Embedding gender equality into organisational culture is often treated as a one-time initiative or a set of project outputs. Without strong internal GE policy mechanisms, clear mandates, procedures, accountability lines and dedicated responsibility, measures tend to fade when leadership changes, workloads rise, or priorities shift. In many cases, weak or irregular self-assessment means institutions lack the evidence base needed to understand the real situation, tailor strategies, and track progress; as a result, even well-designed policies may fail in practice.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Institutionalise GE in the core governance system:** embed GE into internal regulations, strategic documents and standard procedures, not only in project deliverables.
- **Clarify accountability and continuity:** establish clear responsibility chains (who does what, by when) and set periodic review points to maintain momentum over time.
- **Use self-assessment and monitoring as management tools:** conduct responsible, regular assessment with appropriate tools to reveal gaps, adapt measures and turn resistance into practical problem-solving.

¹⁹ [HR Excellence in Research | EURAXESS](#)

- **Sustain the long-term value:** when GE is systematically integrated and monitored, institutions strengthen fairness, reputation, competitive advantage and organisational sustainability.

Lesson 8: Change agents matter, but the system must not depend on individuals

GEP progress in widening ALS HEIs often rests on **a few highly committed people**. Even when a strong core team exists, their contribution can be overlooked and under-supported, and turnover or shifting responsibilities can quickly disrupt continuity. Without formal recognition and organisational anchoring, change agents risk burnout, and GE principles remain dependent on personal motivation rather than embedded in everyday practice.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Strengthen and recognise change agents as a core institutional asset:** AGRIGEP enabled each HEI to build a dedicated and motivated core team with a high level of GE-related competence, often earlier and stronger than would have happened without the project, and these teams became key drivers of institutional change.
- **Formalise and protect the role:** define responsibilities clearly, allocate workload/time, and ensure visibility and recognition so change agents (e.g. institutional GEP Officer) can sustainably champion implementation and influence stakeholders.
- **Build continuity mechanisms that outlast individuals:** document roles, keep simple agendas and brief minutes, and agree ways of working to ensure progress continues when people change.
- **Build on existing structures and networks:** use established alliances (e.g., T4E) and national Communities of Practice for training, exchange and dissemination instead of creating parallel structures. This avoids duplication, fits national and institutional contexts, and increases the chance that practices continue after the project ends. To prevent cooperation from relying on personal contacts, set clear institutional roles (contact points/coordination groups) and simple continuity routines (written agendas, brief minutes, agreed ways of working).

Lesson 9: Stakeholder engagement must be structured, and ALS partners matter

GEP implementation often relied on ad hoc consultations or one-off events, resulting in weak ownership, missed expertise, and limited accountability. In ALS contexts, this gap is amplified by the importance of external partners (farms, agribusiness, industry, rural communities) and by growing internationalisation: without structured engagement, student needs, and safety risks in placements/fieldwork can be overlooked, and GE measures in teaching may remain poorly targeted and underused.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Map stakeholders and align incentives:** identify key internal and external stakeholders, map their interests, and connect GE goals to their priorities to create shared value and deeper engagement.
- **Move from ad hoc to a comprehensive engagement strategy:** plan targeted actions (events, workshops, joint initiatives) that build trust, coordinate resources and sustain collaboration over time.
- **Engage ALS partners intentionally:** establish structured cooperation with farms, industry partners and rural communities; use gender-sensitive collaboration agreements and placement guidelines to strengthen student safety and equitable participation.

- **Treat students as co-owners:** involve student organisations as partners and systematically use student feedback to improve training content and materials, increasing relevance, quality and uptake of GE in teaching.

Lesson 10: Data systems are foundational for credible action

Without a well-organised data collection, monitoring, and reporting system, GE strategies lack precision and credibility, and cannot be effectively planned, implemented, or evaluated. In many cases, consistent sex-disaggregated and intersectional data are missing, with missing or unclear reporting routines. Although building such systems is resource-intensive, their absence makes it difficult to track progress, meet obligations, and communicate results convincingly to internal and external stakeholders.

Aligned AGRIGEP best practices:

- **Establish a structured data and reporting system:** define responsibilities, indicators, timelines and reporting pathways so data collection is routine rather than ad hoc.
- **Combine quantitative and qualitative evidence:** use indicators alongside qualitative tools (e.g., interviews, focus groups) to understand underlying drivers—not only surface symptoms.
- **Use data for transparency and engagement:** integrate key findings into communication and progress reporting to build trust, demonstrate impact, and strengthen stakeholder support.

6. GEP 2.0 - a New Chapter

GEP 2.0 moves beyond the compliance logic of early GEPs by integrating GE into institutional strategies, performance evaluation, teaching, stakeholder engagement, and ALS-specific risks. It thus lays the foundation for structural transformation rather than isolated improvements.

The development of the new GEP 2.0 for each AGRIGEP widening university was based on two processes. Firstly, universities followed the detailed strategic framing concept (described in Chapter 3) to review their existing GEP 1.0 strategy and its implementation effects. In the AGRIGEP project, GEP implementing partners were invited to self-assess their skills and capacities to conduct a change process on GE. Coordinated by Yellow Window, one of AGRIGEP's mentoring partners, this process was completed through cross-analysis, which identified areas for capacity-building and support. The assessments, conducted by both organisations and mentors, identified the areas that each organisation needs to focus on intensively in the next GEP strategy. The entire procedure was supported by capacity-building training provided by mentor partners Yellow Window and Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) during the implementation of the AGRIGEP project. The second process included the actual writing of the new GEPs, led by the mentor partner, the Hungarian Association of Women in Science (NATE). Through a series of internal and joint workshops, expert interviews and bilateral mentoring sessions, the key elements of the new GEPs were defined. The eight thematic areas are presented in Figure 4 below. A tailor-made matrix supported the development of objectives and measurable actions for each area.

GEP 2.0 THEMATIC AREAS

Figure 4. GEP2.0 thematic areas

The inclusion of agriculture- and life-science-specific elements distinguishes GEP 2.0 from the more generic first-generation gender equality plans (GEP 1.0). It ensures that institutional strategies respond directly to sectoral realities such as fieldwork safety, laboratory environments, external industry placements, and rural engagement areas where gendered risks and inequalities are more pronounced. Assessment and self-assessment enabled progress monitoring; training and raising awareness were essential to advance university cultures and reduce stereotypes and resistance. They also fostered the integration of gender aspects into learning and teaching, as well as gender governance across all levels of the university. These processes also contributed to the gradual institutionalisation of gender equality work by embedding GE responsibilities into regular operational routines, strengthening competence across administrative and academic units, and reducing dependence on short-term project structures. The mentoring in GEP 2.0 development, the clear timeline and continuous feedback enabled the implementing HEIs to develop a next-generation GEP 2.0, which

- better reflects their local needs,
- addresses gaps that were identified during the assessments,
- was developed as part of a participatory approach, increasing the ownership of stakeholders, therefore, the impact of the strategy,
- relies on a data collection system developed in the AGRIGEP project that supports transparent monitoring, and
- is an integral part of or clearly connected with other institutional strategies.

By transitioning from compliance-focused GEP 1.0 models to integrated, context-responsive GEP 2.0 strategies, AGRIGEP HEIs are better positioned to align with ERA objectives, enhance institutional competitiveness, and contribute more actively to inclusive and sustainable development in the agriculture and life sciences (ALS) sector. The GEP 2.0 phase, therefore, marks a decisive shift from initial adoption to long-term structural transformation at institutional level.

7. Policy Relevance and Recommendations

With FP10²⁰ discussions underway and GEP 2.0 transitioning from a project compliance document to a long-term institutional practice, the key question is how to secure continuity in contexts where resources and expertise are often scarce. A focused set of priorities can help institutions and policymakers concentrate investments where they have the strongest leverage for sustainable change. Across all levels (institutional, national, EU), three priorities stand out for sustaining progress in widening countries: (1) stable and professionalised GE governance, (2) long-term capacity building, and (3) discipline-specific adaptation for ALS institutions.

The following recommendations (Figure 5) were formulated based on the project's implementation experience and the AGRIGEP project's policy roundtable discussions. These discussions were performed in the frame of the *Second Symposium on Gender Equality for an Inclusive University and Society*²¹ in November 2024 in Koper (Slovenia) at the partner University of Primorska (UP), and at the *Final Conference of the AGRIGEP project*²² In September 2025, the event took place at the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU) in the Czech Republic.

Figure 5. Policy recommendations developed under the AGRIGEP project

In Table 2. AGRIGEP Detailed Policy Recommendations is organised by **governance level** (institutional, national, EU), shown in the first column. The second column highlights the **priority action area** (e.g., governance, training, funding), and the third column summarises the **core recommendations** for that area. This structure enables different stakeholders to quickly identify which actions are most relevant to their respective mandates and responsibilities.

²⁰ 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10) -

https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/tmpmkw0l/fp10_position_paper_05072024.pdf

²¹ <https://agrigep.eu/2024/11/25/reflecting-on-the-success-of-the-second-symposium-on-gender-equality-in-academia/>
<https://fhs.upr.si/up-symposium-on-gender-equality-for-an-inclusive-university-and-society/>

²² <https://agrigep.eu/agrigep-final-conference/>

Table 2. AGRIGEP Detailed Policy Recommendations

Level	Priority area	Key recommendations
Organisational	Formalise GE governance and resourcing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish permanent equality committees/units with clear mandates, dedicated budgets and reporting lines to top management, moving beyond project-based structures Integrate GEPs into core governance (strategic plans, accreditation self-evaluations, promotion criteria, HR Excellence processes) Introduce mandatory GE/equal-opportunity training for all employees and students, repeated regularly as part of GEP implementation
	Make equality training mandatory and systemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embed GE and broader equality content (disability, minorities, anti-discrimination) as compulsory in teacher-training curricula Require a minimum level of pedagogical training for all teaching staff, including researchers without teaching degrees, to improve didactics and inclusive practice
	Strengthen monitoring and internal GE frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop robust internal monitoring systems with common indicators and regular reporting cycles (drawing on tools like EIGE's GEAR) to track implementation and outcomes, not just the existence of a GEP Embed GE in all key strategic documents (research, HR, internationalisation, sustainability) so equality commitments become enforceable institutional norms
	Link GE to high-priority agendas (wellbeing, rankings, internationalisation, digitalisation, sustainability)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Position GEP actions as tools to improve workplace wellbeing, prevent harassment and enhance the experience of international staff and students Make explicit how GE contributes to research and teaching quality, international rankings, digital teaching quality and sustainability transitions (e.g. Green Deal, food systems), reframing GE as value creation rather than mere compliance
National	Secure stable funding and expert capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create stable national funding schemes for GE experts in HEIs and RPOs, capacity-building programmes and mentoring, especially in widening/CEE contexts Recognise ALS as a sector with specific GE needs in national higher education and research policies (beyond generic STEM), including ALS-relevant safety protocols, rural innovation and fieldwork risks
	Align accreditation and teacher education with GE goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate mandatory GE and equality components into accreditation standards for teacher-training programmes and, where possible, for academic pedagogical training Encourage QA and accreditation bodies to require documented GE measures and monitoring systems in institutional reviews
	Implement legal frameworks on leadership balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure national transposition and effective implementation of the EU directive on gender quotas, and encourage publicly owned companies and public institutions (including universities) to align leadership targets with these obligations
EU	Reinforce GE instruments in the next Framework Programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain and strengthen GEP eligibility and related GE instruments in FP10, with particular support for lagging regions via targeted budgets, mentoring and capacity-building calls

Support regional and sectoral networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish and fund a dedicated CEE Gender Equality Network for HEIs with EU-level recognition to coordinate peer learning, training, mentoring and ALS-specific knowledge sharing Better connect regional networks to international ones (e.g. via UNIDO), and provide long-term resources for networking beyond short-term schemes (COST, Interreg, Erasmus+)
Develop sector-specific GE strategies beyond STEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complement STEM-focused strategies with discipline- and sector-specific GE roadmaps (including ALS), supported by expert groups and integrated into EU-level policy frameworks, recognising fieldwork risks, rural innovation and agri-food value chains as distinct governance challenges
Address GE in internationalisation, digitalisation and sustainability policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure EU policies on internationalisation, digitalisation (including AI and online teaching), and sustainability transitions systematically integrate GE and inclusive practices, reinforcing the role of ALS institutions in achieving the Green Deal and SDG 5

8. Institutional Transformation: The way forward

This policy brief reviews the main obstacles that AGRIGEP implementing institutions in Central and Eastern European region have encountered in the evolution from their GEP 1.0 to GEP 2.0. Drawing on partners' experience, it outlines the key phases of revising GEPs into tailored, sector-specific strategies that can more effectively advance gender equality within each institution. The shift to GEP 2.0 is therefore not a simple update, but a deeper commitment to structural change.

The lessons documented here show that sustained political support, clear governance structures, and long-term capacity-building are crucial for maintaining momentum beyond the project's duration. Institutional transformation is rarely linear. GEP implementation in widening countries requires iterative adaptation, continuous feedback loops, and strong organisational learning mechanisms. Supporting GEP 2.0, therefore, means investing in resilience, not just compliance.

Enhancing gender balance is a strategic priority for Europe^{14, 23}. By implementing targeted policies and fostering a culture of inclusion, Europe can harness the full potential of its workforce, driving competitiveness and sustainable economic growth. We believe that universities play a pivotal role in fostering competitiveness, inclusiveness, diversity, and gender equality in knowledge-based societies. Acknowledging cultural differences is key to approaching transformative agendas in higher education and research. International networking could provide support, enhancing synergies and providing complementary expertise and experience.

By leveraging the full potential of every individual, regardless of their gender, Europe can drive innovation, improve decision-making, and foster sustainable economic growth. This policy brief highlights the significance of gender equality in higher education institutions and offers recommendations to promote gender balance, thereby contributing to the region's economic growth. Looking ahead, institutional transformation will require not only the effective implementation of GEP 2.0 but also continuous adaptation to emerging challenges, such as digitalisation, demographic change, and evolving labour markets. By embedding GE into organisational strategies, governance systems, and sector-specific practices, especially in ALS and HEIs, they can position themselves as resilient, innovative, and socially responsible actors in the ERA.

²³ 2025 Report on Gender Equality in the EU. Luxembourg (2025). Publications Office of the European Union. doi:10.2838/5262357 https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/055fdbab-5786-425e-a072-652bf53d8fe4_en?filename=Gender%20Equality%20Report.